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Impact Factor: 6.049

Leveraging Collective Action by Self Help Groups for Sustainable Food Security among Households in Nyakach Sub County, Kenya

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Abstract

Household food security in Kenya has been deteriorating steadily with one in every two households classified as absolutely food poor. Food insecure households are concentrated among the female-headed households especially in rural areas, the urban poor and resource poor households that live in high potential agricultural areas. Nyakach Sub County is typically dry, particularly the Lower and West Nyakach divisions, with a single rainy season (March to May), and relies heavily on other farming activities, such as goat, cattle and sheep keeping as its primary form of agriculture. However, the agricultural industry in the area is currently underperforming, resulting in low food production. The sub-county relies on imported food as a supplement to locally produced food. The records at the Sub-County Social Services Office indicate that the area has 796 SHGs, as at December 2023. Based on the foregoing, the study examined how leveraging on collective action by Self Help Groups influence sustainable food security among households in Nyakach Sub County, Kenya. This study was grounded on the Theory of Collective Action and was guided by mixed research design, with both quantitative and qualitative methodologies of data collection. The target population was 796 SHG members in different SHGs in Nyakach Sub County, from which 75 respondents were administered with structured questionnaires for quantitative data as well as 4 focus group discussions for qualitative data. The information collected through questionnaires were tabulated, coded, edited and analyzed by using the statistical techniques live averages, percentages, standard deviations, and correlation using SPSS version 26, while qualitative data were analysed through thematic content analysis. The findings of the study demonstrated that SHGs were relevant in pooling of resources through collective action and hence contributed highly in enhancing sustainable food security among the SHG members through the increase of food production and the economic activities undertaken by these SHGs like savings and working with financial institutions for getting loans and for input acquisition and capacity building of SHGs members have played a big role in sustaining food security among the households. Therefore, the study recommends that there is need to develop SHGs' organizational and resource capacity to profit even more households. This could increase access to agricultural production resources hence increased farm production and growth in farm income.

Keywords; *Collective Action; Households; Nyakach sub-county; Self Help Group; Sustainable Food Security*

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Food security is a fundamental human right, yet millions of people continue to suffer the ravages of hunger and malnutrition (World Health Organization 2020). Food security exists when all people at all times have physical and economic access to adequate, safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preference (Ben Hassen, & El Bilali, 2022; Pingali, 2021). Household food security is the application of this concept at the family level with individuals within the family being the focus of concern. Fleetwood, (2020) points out that

food security encompasses food availability through farm production, storage or imports; and the access that people have to food through their purchasing power in markets. On the other hand, food access is determined by an individual's or household's access to adequate resources or entitlements; derived from human and physical capital assets, access to common resources and a variety of social contracts at family, community and state level, over which a person can establish command given the legal, political, economic and social arrangement of the community (Pawlak, & Kołodziejczak, 2020; Thompson, & Amoroso, 2011).

A household's access to food is further determined by the opportunities it has to utilize or exchange those resources to meet its food and material needs (Schleifer & Sun, 2020). Purchasing powers of a household, evolution of real incomes and food prices have been found to be important in ensuring food access (He, Liu, & Cui, 2021; Arimond, & Ruel, 2014). Udmale, et al., (2020) indicated that, people go hungry in spite of an abundant supply of food at the global level because they cannot obtain sufficient quantity or quality food due to poverty. Pawlak, & Kołodziejczak, (2020) concluded that while food availability highlights the supply of food at national level and production at farm level, food accessibility demonstrates the effective demand and purchasing power of households. In the last decade, the number of the undernourished people globally has increased slowly but steadily even before the twin food and economic crises of 2009 (Eskola, et al. 2020; World Health Organization, 2023; Snapp, & Fisher, 2015). In the year 2023, the number of people suffering from food insecurity increased from 848 million in 2022 to 923 million (UNICEF, 2021; Khondker, et al., 2021; Khoury, et al., 2019). In Kenya, a third of the population is food insecure with two million people needing urgent interventions at any given time. This number increases during drought, heavy rains or floods with arid and semi-arid areas (ASALs) being more affected.

Empirical evidence has shown that women are the engine that drives agriculture in developing countries especially in the Sub Saharan Africa (SSA) (Cassimon, Fadare, and Mavrotas, 2022; Cassimon, Fadare, & Mavrotas, 2021). They play an important role as food producers, natural resource managers, income earners and, caretakers of household food security (Bhattacharya, Misra, & Hussain, 2016). They produce 50% of food globally, while in Africa, Asia and Latin America, they produce 60-80% of staple food (World Bank, 2023). Women are therefore crucial in ensuring household food security. They make food available in the household by engaging in varied activities such as small-scale farming, livestock keeping and the gathering of wild foods (Atieno, 2016). They also access food through purchases and the collection of food donations derived outside of the home (UNICEF; 2021; Popkin, & Slining, 2013). However, women are faced with a lot of constraints in ensuring household food security (Haddad et al. 2023). They have limited access to financial, land and social assets and have fewer opportunities to improve their knowledge and skills (Devi, 2022). In response to the difficulties and responsibilities facing them, women have formed organizations based on traditional informal structures, governmental and international agencies to help them cope with the myriad of problems facing them and their communities collectively rather than as individuals (Udmale, et al., 2020; Kennedy, & Moursi, 2019).

In Kenya, 70% of the population lives in the rural areas, while the agricultural sector employs about 90% of the rural dwellers (World Health Organization 2023). The majority of these rural dwellers engaged in agriculture are small-holder farmers who produce about 9% of the total agricultural output of the country on less than 2 hectares of land. Fifty (50) percent of total land area in the country is potential agricultural land with only 48.5% of this area being under cultivation, while only 7% of the total irrigable land is being put to use. The study area-Nyakach Sub County is typically dry, particularly the Lower and West Nyakach divisions, with a single rainy season (March to May), and relies heavily on other farming activities, such as goat keeping, among other livestock, as its primary form of agriculture. Those living in the far north, Lower Nyakach, near the Nyando Floodplains, however, frequently cultivate green vegetables and maize on the wet lands. The remainder of the sub-county depends on a single rainfall season to cultivate (albeit on a small scale) sorghum, cassava, and millet in addition to keeping goats and sheep. The agricultural industry in the area is currently underperforming, resulting in low food production overall. The sub-county relies on imported food as a supplement to locally produced food. The overreliance on rice as a source of income and for brick production, combined with the

neglect of other food crops, has exacerbated the food insecurity and commercial agriculture. However, records at the Sub-County Social Services Office indicate the area has 796 SHGs, as at December 2023. The study therefore examined how leveraging on collective action by Self Help Groups influence sustainable food security among households in Nyakach Sub County, Kenya.

2.0 Statement of the Problem

Household food security in Kenya has been deteriorating steadily with one in every two households classified as absolutely food poor. Food insecure households are concentrated among the female-headed households especially in rural areas, the urban poor and resource poor households that live in high potential agricultural areas. Most households depend on both foods produced from their own farms and also purchased food for their daily nutrient intake. Although women play a crucial role in household food security, most are resource poor. They lack access to resources such as income, credit and land, which are essential in agricultural production and purchase of food. Legal and cultural reasons limit women's right to access credit. This is because land which most women do not own is usually required as collateral for loan by commercial banks. Credit is more accessible to women groups than to individual women. It has been argued that income in the hands of women has more significant influence on household food security than that in the hands of men. Lack of income in the hands of women and inadequate knowledge on the agricultural production could be one of the causes of household food insecurity in Nyakach Sub County. However, there is insufficient empirical evidence on how collective action by women self-help groups can be harnessed for sustainable food security in Nyakach Sub County.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theory of Collective Action

The Theory of Collective Action, originally formulated by economist Mancur Olson in 1965, explores how individuals with common interests can collaborate to achieve outcomes that benefit the group as a whole (Olson, 1965). The theory articulates that people who share common traits are more likely to share social networks, affecting subsequent interaction and cooperation. People who are like minded may have preferences for working with each other; they may also have better knowledge on how to sanction and reward each other, which is important for establishing cooperation. The theory provides a novel and original explanation of group behaviour which convincingly contradicts established theories.

In collective action theory, a group should be treated as an assembly of rational individuals, not as an entity itself. Olson's main assumptions in deriving the theory were thus methodological individualism and rational behaviour of individuals. Thus, Olson assumed that group behaviour should be explained by economic calculus determined by the incentives and costs that each member of a group faces. In other words, Olson applied economic method into social phenomenon, whose understanding was at best vague. In Olson's view, even if individuals do share a common goal and even if transaction costs of organizing a group are nil, this is not enough for a collective action to take place. We should rather consider the relation of benefits to costs on an individual, not group level. First, even if collective benefits are large, the benefit gained by a single individual will probably be much smaller and may not cover the costs borne. And second, if all members of a group will benefit from the collective action, then there is no incentive for an individual to engage in these activities.

Small groups provide collective goods only through voluntary action of their members (Matshe, 2019; Crush, & Frayne, 2021). The incentives to free-ride or shirk are limited here by social control or by transparent effects of group action. However, a small group can take up a successful collective action even if only one member of the group will cover all the costs – under the condition that the benefits will outweigh the costs borne by this particular individual (Harvey, et al. 2014; Allen, & De Brauw, 2018). Similarly, business lobbies often gain privileges because they are organized not as the whole business class, but as oligopolistic branches which pursue their own particular interests. According to Tembo (2015), this occurs because having a common interest

or concern among members of a group (community, region, country) or any other grouping does not mean they will act to maximise gains for the whole group.

This theory informs this study because it provides a framework for understanding how SHGs can facilitate cooperation among farmers to overcome common challenges and achieve shared goals, including boosting agricultural food production. By leveraging the collective strength of their members, SHGs can contribute significantly to agricultural development and food security.

2.2 Collective Action by SHGs and Sustainable Food Security in Households

Helmerich, et al., (2017) carried out a study on achieving sustainable food security and poverty reduction through consumer cooperatives in Hyderabad, India. A survey to study the economic and social background, the functioning and future perspectives of over 200 members of different cooperative groups in rural and urban areas around the future megacity Hyderabad, begun in September 2006. The study revealed that members of the cooperative and SHG groups in rural and urban areas, despite their low earnings and educational levels, were interested in making an effort to better their lives, especially by enhancing their food security. On the other hand, managerial and organizational limits restrict certain approaches and methods. The women expressed their opinions about these concerns and problems. The study also revealed the nature of socio-economic impacts on the lives of the members. It looked at present empirical realities in the framework of Security, Empowerment, Civil Society and Rural Development, with the assumption that the vulnerability of low income households regarding liquidity, health and nutrition in the context of rapidly expanding cities is a prime obstacle in the sustainable development of women. In the process, various issues were noticed which were found to be relevant for the performance and future direction of Women's Consumer Cooperatives in Hyderabad.

Deshmukh, and Singh (2023) carried out a study on sustainable rural livelihood security (SRLS) index through women self-help groups. A random sampling method was utilized to select SHG households. Employing a 'mixed method of research,' data on the conditions both before and after SHG involvement were gathered from a total of '240' sampled households. The study underscored a positive and noteworthy influence of microfinance on the sustainable rural livelihood security of SHG households. Microfinance within SHGs served as a tool for elevating those below the poverty line to a more prosperous status on the SRLS index. The endurance of sustainable rural livelihood security for SHG households was intertwined with factors such as their monthly income, sources of information, received training, microfinance utilization, loan repayment, outstanding loans, and attitude. Consequently, a significant policy suggestion emerged that policymakers, microfinance institutions, experts in technology, and development practitioners should consider these crucial variables to enhance the sustainable livelihood security of the rural poor, particularly in nations with modest to middle-level incomes like India.

Bareh, and Ghosh (2018) studied Self Help Group (SHG) Movement in Meghalaya, assessing the Potential Option to Improve Income and Livelihood Security of Farm Households. The study revealed an increase in number of SHGs from two in the year 1995 to as high as 9108 in 2010, most of which were female SHGs. Government departments and NGOs were the major SHG promoters in Meghalaya. Although promotion of savings and credit was found to be the major reason for formation of SHGs as about 95 per cent of the members were under the poverty line; however, it has been transformed to an instrument of empowerment and income generating activities resulting into the improved income and livelihood security of rural households in Meghalaya. The major income generating activity was found to be rearing farm animals and was taken up by 25 per cent of the members. The other income generating activities of SHGs were horticulture-based which was being taken up by 16 per cent of the SHG members followed by agriculture-based activity which was being taken up by 14 per cent. The major problem faced by SHG members related to functioning of SHG was lack of adequate funds and lack of knowledge that required the intervention of extension functionaries in the state.

Maina (2020) sought to establish the influence of participation in self-help groups on socio-economic empowerment of women in Tigania West Sub-County, Meru County, Kenya. The study was guided by the

family systems theory. The study used descriptive and exploratory research design and the target population was all women in self-help groups in Tigania West Sub-County in which accessible population was 3610 women from 25 registered self-help groups. A sample size of 150 was selected through stratified simple random sampling. The study results indicated that participation in self-help groups helped in improving the confidence of the group members, social networks of the self-group members, credit access and level of income amongst women in self-help groups. However, the reviewed study only looked at how participation in self-help groups influence socio-economic empowerment of women and not on its contributions to the sustainable food security among the households.

In a related study, Digo, Koros, and Everlyne, (2014) researched on household food security among women groups in Kaiti Division, Kenya. This study was designed to determine the relationship between household food security through improved access to education credit and other productive resources as a result of collective action of the women self-help groups. The study used a cross sectional survey design. A sample of 234 respondents was selected through simple random sampling, with 141 being group members and 93 non group members. Data was analysed using SPSS package version 17 for windows and presented using frequencies, percentages and multiple regression. The study revealed that household food security was significantly and positively influenced by participation of women farmers in women groups ($F = 9.761, p = 0.000$). However, the reviewed study only focused on how participation in self-help groups influence household food security among women famers and not the sustainable food security among women SHG members in the region.

2.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. *Conceptual framework on collective action by self-help groups for sustainable food security among households in Nyakach sub county, Kenya*

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study used mixed methods with both quantitative and qualitative methodologies of collecting data. Mixed methods research design refers to a methodology that combines qualitative and quantitative research techniques within a single study or program of inquiry. This approach offers researchers the flexibility to explore complex research questions from multiple perspectives, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation.

3.2 Target population, Sampling Size and Technique

The populations from which the primary data were collected comprised 336 SHG members in different SHGs in Nyakach Sub County. There were a total of 21 active SHGs in Nyakach Sub County with 336 members in total. For determining the sample size, the study used the formula by Dr. Alain Bouchard stating that for the population under 1,000,000 individuals, the sample can be 96 with assumed error of 10% and 90% of precision

(Bouchard, 2019). This can be elaborated in the following figures:

N: Population size equals 336 SHGs members in Nyakach Sub County.

No: Sample size when the population size goes towards infinite is 96 Nc: Corrected sample size

$N_c = \frac{N * N_o}{N_c} = \frac{(336 * 96)}{336} = 75$. Thus, the sample size was 75

The 75 respondents were randomly obtained from 336 SHG members of which semi-structured questionnaires were administered to Seventy-Five (75) randomly selected SHG members.

3.3 Data Collection Instruments

In order to collect their written reflections on the contribution of SHGs in enhancing food security in households, a semi-structured questionnaire was developed and distributed to the respondents. Broadly, the questionnaire covers various aspects such as extent of assets acquisition, savings, level of income generation, living standards, expenses, trainings, SHGs membership, households farming and agricultural productivity (inputs and outputs analysis). In addition, the study used 4 focus group discussion and observation.

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

The methods used to collect data included the use of semi-structured questionnaire. To further ascertain data collected through primary data collection methods, various SHG documents were analyzed and pertinent data regarding group meeting attendance, individual savings and loan, and the general performance of the SHGs were gathered. All categories of primary data collection were conducted in both English and Luo languages after translating the questions from English to Luo language.

3.5 Data Processing and Analysis

The primary step in analyzing quantitative data was checking the questionnaire for consistency and errors. The quantitative data collected were tabulated according to their frequency and percentage. The information collected were tabulated, coded, edited and analyzed by using the statistical techniques live averages, percentages, standard deviations, standard errors, and correlation using SPSS version 26. For qualitative data, the study used thematic content analysis.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Background Characteristics of the Respondents

The personal data of the respondents; age, education level and marital status of the SHG members were studied and the results were as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Age of respondents

Background Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Age		
Less than 20 years	1	1.3
Between 20 and 35	22	29.3
Between 35 and 50	26	34.7
Between 50 and 65	19	25.3
Greater or equal 65 years	7	9.3
Education level		
Illiterate	16	21.3
Primary	52	69.3
Secondary	7	9.3
Marital Status		
Single	10	13.3
Married	63	84.0
Widow	2	2.7
Total	75	100.0

This table gives the age categories of the respondents where a big number of the respondents (34.7%) were found between 35 and 50 years and only 1 respondent had less than 20 years. This showed that 65% of these farmers were in their middle age (i.e. relatively active). This portrays that most of the members of SHGs were in their active and productive age where they could put in their best for optimum agricultural productivity. In terms of education, the table shows that the majority of members of SHG (69.3%) had primary level of education, while 9.3% had attended secondary school and 21.3% were illiterate. This implies that the education level of the SHG members was very low. Education of the members played an important role in decision making and accessing crucial production information. Paltasingh, and Goyari, (2018) also established that education equips farmers with the necessary knowledge and skills to implement modern agricultural practices effectively. This includes techniques for crop cultivation, soil management, pest control, water conservation, and livestock rearing. Farmers educated in these methods are often able to achieve higher yields and better quality produce. Therefore, this helps SHG members in gaining skills and adapt to new technologies. On marital status, the study revealed that 13% of the respondents were single, 84% were married and 2.7% were widows. The fact that a big part of these SHG members were married showed that they were adept at decision making regarding the increase of production and income for their living standards improvement.

4.2 Reasons for joining SHGs

Respondents were asked to indicate reasons for joining the SHG and the results were as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Reasons for Joining the SHG

Reasons for Joining SHG	Frequency	Percent
1. To increase the agriculture knowledge, to increase the income from the Agriculture production, to get a loan	1	1.3
2. To save, to increase the agriculture knowledge	5	6.7
3. To increase the income from the Agriculture production	27	36.0
4. To Save, to get a loan	2	2.7
5. To save, to increase the income from the Agriculture Production	2	2.7
6. To save, to increase the agriculture knowledge, to increase the income from the Agriculture production	12	16.0
7. To save, to increase the agriculture knowledge, to get a loan	1	1.3
8. To save, to increase the agriculture knowledge, to increase the income from the Agriculture production, to get a loan	6	8.0
9. To save, to increase the income from the Agriculture production, to get a loan	15	20.0
10. To increase the income from the Agriculture production, to get a loan	2	2.7
Total	75	100.0

The table shows that the major reason for joining the SHGs was to save, to increase the income from the agriculture production, to get a loan and to increase the agriculture knowledge and most of the members have joined the SHG for saving and increase the income from the agriculture production (36%). This was most important, for increasing the income and the agriculture production for sustaining food security among the households. These findings concur with that of Kumar, Suar, and Mishra (2018) who also found that one of the primary reasons women join SHGs was to gain access to financial resources. SHGs provide opportunities for women to save money collectively, access credit facilities, and engage in income-generating activities (Chaudhury, & Misra, 2018). By pooling their resources, women can secure loans at lower interest rates than those offered by traditional moneylenders, enabling them to invest in businesses or meet household needs.

Table 3: Trainings Received by SHGs Members

The Training Received Titles	Frequency	Valid Percent
1. Income generating activities	1	1.8
2. Social Mobilization, income generating activities, Use of improved seeds, fertilizers and pest management	1	1.8
3. Marketing	1	1.8
4. Social Mobilization, Income generating activities	1	1.8
5. Use of improved seeds, fertilizers and pest management	25	44.6
6. Social Mobilization, Marketing	1	1.8
7. Income generating activities, use of improved seeds, fertilizers, pest management	9	16.1
8. Income generating activities, marketing	3	5.4
9. Use of improved seeds, fertilizers and pest management, Marketing	5	8.9
10. Social Mobilization, use of improved seeds, fertilizers and pest management	1	1.8
11. Social Mobilization, income generating activities, Use of improved seeds, fertilizers and pest management, marketing	1	1.8
12. Income generating activities, use of improved seeds, fertilizers and pest management, marketing	5	8.9
13. Social Mobilization, use of improved seeds, fertilizers and pest management, Marketing	1	1.8
Total	56	100.0

Table 3 shows the list of all trainings delivered to SHGs members whereby 44.6% said that they have been trained on the use of improved seeds, fertilizers and pest management, which showed the great role of SHG in capacity building of SHG members, for increasing the food production, hence the sustainability of the food security. All kinds of trainings given to these SHG members were oriented to the improvement of agribusiness. Similarly, from the focus group discussion, it was found that through SHG membership, agricultural trainings take place, which then improve the members' productivity through farming. Here is what one of the members had to say during the focus group discussion;

Through SHG membership, I am able to access agricultural training programs covering various aspects of crop cultivation, including land preparation, seed selection, planting techniques, irrigation methods, and pest management. We also learn about suitable crops for their region, crop rotation practices, and the use of organic fertilizers and pesticides. (FGD 3)

These findings agree with that of Matshe, (2019) who similarly found that many SHGs offer agricultural training programs and workshops to their members. These capacity-building initiatives can enhance farmers' skills and knowledge in various aspects of agriculture, including soil management, pest control, and water conservation. As farmers become more skilled, they can improve their agricultural practices, leading to increased food production.

4.3 Agriculture production, Profitability and the Role Played by the SHGs

In agriculture, the increase of production and profitability by all means is a necessity. The SHG members can play a greater role in increasing production, productivity and profitability and this can be of great importance in sustaining food security.

Table 4: Production before joining the SHG and after joining the SHG

Production quantity per class Interval (Kg)	Production quantity (Kg) before joining SHG		Production quantity (Kg) after joining SHG	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Less than 100	49	65.3	9	12.0
Between 100 and 200	18	24.0	4	5.3
Between 200 and 300	3	4.0	15	20.0
Between 300 and 400	1	1.3	12	16.0
Between 400 and 500	1	1.3	11	14.7
Between 500 and 600	0	0.0	4	5.3
Between 600 and 700	0	0.0	3	4.0
Between 700 and 800	0	0.0	3	4.0
Between 800 and 900	1	1.3	3	4.0
Between 900 and 1000	1	1.3	3	4.0
Greater or equal 1000	1	1.3	8	10.7
Total	75	100.0	75	100.0

Table 4 shows that the production increased after joining the SHG when comparing to before joining the SHG. For example, 65.3% of the respondents before joining the SHG have had the production which is less than 100 Kilograms and only 1 respondent had more than 1 ton. After joining the SHG, only 12% had less than 100 Kilograms and 8 respondents had more than 1 ton. Similarly, during the focus group discussion with the SHG members, it was established that food production was increased after joining the SHGs. Here is an excerpt of one of the respondents;

Being members of SHGs has helped us in pooling resources together, enabling us to access inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, and tools. This pooled purchasing power has hugely helped us afford higher quality inputs, leading to increased productivity and better crop yields. (FGD, 1)

From the above findings, it can be deduced that joining a SHG have multifaceted benefits for agricultural food production, ranging from improved access to resources and markets to enhanced knowledge and skills among farmers. These findings concur with that of Deshmukh, & Singh, (2023) who also established that by leveraging collective action and mutual support, SHGs can empower farmers to enhance their productivity and contribute to food security and livelihood improvement in their communities. Similarly, Atieno, (2016) found that by participating in these initiatives, women acquire new skills that enhance their employability or enable them to start their own businesses. This aspect of SHGs contributes to economic independence and reduces dependency on others for livelihoods.

4.4 Savings and Food Production

SHG members were first asked to indicate their level of savings before and after joining the SHGs. Table 5 shows the responses.

Table 5: Savings before joining the SHGs and after joining the SHGs

Amount of Saving per class Interval (KSH)	Saving before joining SHG		Saving after joining SHG	
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
No saving	48	64.0	0	0.0
Less 10,000	10	13.3	14	18.7
Between 10,000 and 20,000	4	5.3	25	33.3
Between 20,000 and 30,000	6	8.0	10	13.3
Between 30,000 and 40,000	1	1.3	6	8.0
Between 40,000 and 50,000	4	5.3	2	2.7
Between 50,000 and 60,000	0	0.0	3	4.0

Between 60,000 and 70,000	0	0.0	3	4.0
Between 70,000 and 80,000	0	0.0	3	4.0
Between 80,000 and 90,000	1	1.3	0	0.0
Between 90,000 and 100,000	1	1.3	3	4.0
Greater or equal 100,000	0	0.0	6	8.0
Total	75	100.0	75	100.0

Table 5 shows that the savings increased after joining the SHGs in comparison to before joining the SHG. For example 64% of the respondents said that they had not saved before joining the SHG and no one had saved more than KES 100,000. After joining farmers' SHGs, everyone was saving and 6 people saved more than KES 100,000. This shows that joining self-help groups increases saving practices among the members. Similarly, during the focused group session with the SHG members, one of the members had this to say;

Ever since I joined my Self Help Group, I have been able to save significant amounts as compared to when I was not a member of any group. From my savings, I have been able to improve my agricultural food production practices such as buying fertilizers and practicing modern farming to increase food production (FGD 2)

This finding is in agreement with that of Digo, Koros & Everlyne, (2014) who also found that participation in SHGs often encourages members to save regularly. Through group dynamics, peer pressure, and collective decision-making, members are motivated to save more consistently. As a result, the savings per individual member tend to increase over time.

Table 6: Pearson Correlations between respondents' Savings and Agricultural Food Production

Correlations		Food Production	Saving after joining SHG
Production	Pearson Correlation	1	.570**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	75	75
Saving after joining SHG	Pearson Correlation	.570**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	75	75

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Food production influences the saving of SHG members. (The correlation coefficient is 57% which means there is a moderate correlation between food production and saving of SHG members. The family saving has increased after joining Self-Help Groups. This result is very obvious as the Self-Help Groups promote the saving habit among the group members. Similarly, Digo, Koros, & Everlyne, (2014) found that SHG members savings can play a big role in farm production increase by helping the SHG members to get improved seeds, fertilizers and other necessary inputs without any hitch and may help these farmers to meet the necessary needs for the day and hence income, production and the living standards are improved through the savings which are important in economic development of each and every one

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, leveraging collective action through self-help groups (SHGs) can be a strategy for achieving sustainable food security among households. The findings of the study therefore demonstrated that SHGs were pooling resources through collective action and hence contributed in enhancing sustainable food security among SHG members through the increase of food production and the economic activities played by these SHGs. Activities like savings and working with financial institutions for getting loans and for input acquisition and capacity building of the SHGs members played a critical role in sustaining food security among the households. SHGs facilitate the sharing of knowledge and best practices among members related to sustainable agricultural techniques such as organic farming, water conservation, crop rotation, and integrated pest management. This

exchange of information can help members adopt more sustainable farming methods. By pooling their resources, SHG members can collectively purchase inputs such as seeds, fertilizers and equipment at lower costs. This not only reduces individual expenses but also enables access to quality inputs that promote sustainable agriculture, such as organic fertilizers and bio pesticides. The study recommends that there is need to develop SHGs' organizational and resource capacity to profit even more households. This could increase access to agricultural production resources hence increased farm production and growth in farm income. Groups which are not performing well should be supported to expand their productive opportunities in order to meaningfully improve rural livelihoods and food security. This assistance could be through partnerships with private and government agencies, which could promote groups' access to a wider range of services and increase their effectiveness in provision of resources and services such as farm inputs, information, accessing markets and financial services. Given the financial implications inherent in active participation in groups, the policymakers might need to address the disparities across households in group participation rates and in services accessible through the groups to ensure that the poor benefit from group participation that often requires meeting upfront costs before realizing benefits. This measure is needed to fully realize the potential of groups in improving the welfare of the poor and the not so poor within the community.

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